

EMBL-EBI Introduction

- EMBL-EBI is a global leader in bioinformatics: the science of storing, analysing and sharing large biological datasets.
- By sharing our expertise and through collaboration, we help researchers realise the potential of 'bigdata', enhancing their ability to exploit complex information to make discoveries that benefit mankind.
- We are a non-profit, intergovernmental organisation funded by EMBL member states.
- Our 600 staff represent 57 nationalities and we welcome a regular stream of visiting scientists throughout the year.
- We are located on the Wellcome Genome Campus in Hinxton, Cambridge in the United Kingdom.

Bioinformatics services

Genes, genomes & variation

Proteins: sequences, families, domains & motifs

Chemical biology

Expression

Molecular & cellular structures

Pathways & systems

HPC Infrastructure

- We operate a sizeable infrastructure for our 500+ Service and Research users.
- Over 400 heterogeneous nodes with 48 Cores Intel CPUs.
- Large Memory nodes (2TB) for application requiring large in memory processing.
- Over 60 Nvidia (A100 and V100) GPUs to support AI/ML and LLM applications.
- Over 400PB archival storage and 5PB flash storage for scratch space.
- SLURM Scheduler for job scheduling and resource management.

400
Compute
Nodes

20k+
Compute
Cores

60+
Nvidia
GPUs

400PB
Archival
Storage

5PB
Scratch
Storage

20+
Large
Memory
Nodes

HPC Services

- HPC team is responsible for overseeing HPC compute infrastructure operations.
- Hardware management, OS Upgrades, Scientific applications support, SLURM scheduler management.
- We also provide user application support on best effort basis.
- As part of Green computing initiative, we use Slurm power saving feature to dynamically power on/off compute nodes.

Scientific
Applications

HPC Workflows

User Trainings and
Workshops

Data Ingestion /
Processing

Infrastructure Provisioning and Monitoring

- We provision our Compute nodes using Warewulf stateless provisioning.
- Our service nodes are stateful which are provisioned using traditional pxe boot.
- Ansible is used for Configuration management on Compute nodes.
- Infrastructure monitoring is done via CheckMK for In-Band and Out-of-Band monitoring.
- We use Grafana and Prometheus for SLURM Scheduler monitoring.

Ansible for
Configuration
Management

CheckMK for
Infrastructure
Monitoring

Warewulf for
Stateless
Provisioning

Interactive HPC

- To support interactive use of our HPC systems, we offer Open OnDemand instance at our site.
- We support various Interactive applications E.g. Jupyter Lab, Rstudio Server, VMD, PyCharm Editor etc.
- Our Interactive HPC solution allows users to perform data visualisation and processing on the same platform.
- It also minimizes the unnecessary offloading data from HPC systems to user laptops for post processing.
- Open OnDemand closely integrates with Job scheduler and offers access to HPC resources via Web Portal.